

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE WORKS OF THE WRITER SADIK GARAYEV DEDICATED TO OUR HISTORICAL CHRONICLE OF VICTORY AS A VALUABLE SOURCE OF INFORMATION IN THE GROWTH OF THE YOUNG GENERATION IN THE NATIONAL SPIRIT

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Abstract

The article discusses the books of the writer Sadig Garayev “Heroism No. “N”” and “Ideology of Azerbaijanism” and their role in educating the future generation in the national spirit. These works are valuable works that will play an important role in preserving our historical memory and developing our national identity. In the work, all our brave sons of Azerbaijan, from the first years of the war for Karabakh to our Victory, are glorified as the heroism of the united Azerbaijani people. The author describes the great victory with both sadness and joy, but sees our martyrs, Mr. Supreme Commander-in-Chief, who showed endless selflessness and heroism above all else. The memory of the brave sons and daughters of Azerbaijan who were martyred, went missing, and later died from serious wounds in the battles for the integrity of our lands, in the Karabakh war, should be dear to every Azerbaijani. Because they are national heroes who did not hesitate to give their lives for this homeland when necessary, and fearlessly and courageously went against the enemy.

This book, written about our heroes and our victory, will be a special gift and memory for future generations. Because from time to time, our ancestors forcibly tore our homeland apart, inch by inch, and gave it to our enemy. These occupations also reached Karabakh. During the 44-day Patriotic War, Karabakh was liberated from occupation thanks to the determination of the Supreme Commander-in-Chief and the power of the unity of the people and the army. However, when our lands were liberated from occupation, the Azerbaijani people sacrificed thousands of their children. The article notes that the books also contain memories of the fighting path of the brave men who died for the territorial integrity of Azerbaijan. It is highlighted that it is a very important issue to write down our history, our victory, the heroism shown by our martyrs and veterans, and to write books in order to avoid genocides again and prevent our lands from being occupied again.

Keywords: Writer, Sadig Garayev, heroism number “N”, “Azerbaijanism ideology, young generation, information provision.

Introduction

Resource is the source of stock of the different means. There are resources of adjoining information resources of raw material, energy, labor and finance in the modern society too. Another any resources from information resources disappears during use. For instance, fuel burnt and finishes, finance means is spent and. But information resources do not finish, they are a lot of to use. One of such information resources is socio-political resources. There are 2 kind of socio-political information resources: 1. Initial socio-political information resources 2. Second socio-political information resources.

Printed primary documents have a main role in development of socio-political information resources. In the primary sources printed about information resource 46 covers of the multivolume of “Our independence is eternal” is necessary (1997-2013)[5, p.24]

Patriotism, which is considered one of the important elements of the ideology of Azerbaijanism, plays a fundamental role in the formation of the national spirit and the identification of national identity. In this sense, the elevation of the national spirit and the promotion of patriotism unambiguously pave the way for the further strengthening of national unity and solidarity in our country, the attachment of the younger

generation to their land and homeland. Naturally, one of the greatest tasks in this matter falls on our literature. Thus, literary examples reflecting national traditions form the basis for the growth of the people in the national spirit.

The content of the books “Heroism No. “N” [2] and “Ideology of Azerbaijanism” [3], which are the product of the thinking of the prominent representative of modern Azerbaijani prose, the well-known writer Sadig Garayev, invites humanity to peace and humanism, demonstrates objectivity and honesty. They glorify attachment to the homeland, to the land, appreciate courage, fearlessness and heroism, and give priority to truth and justice. The writer supports the youth, calls for respect for language, religion, and national and spiritual values that have been formed over many years and passed down from generation to generation on the basis of the principle of inheritance, promotes the exaltation of our glorious history, thinkers, and leaders. He praises the nature of the homeland, makes people love it, values customs and traditions, and justifies the philosophy of the idea of Azerbaijanism.

Problem setting

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The purpose of explaining the role of Sadig Garayev's books "Heroism No. "N"" and "Ideology of Azerbaijanism" in the education of the future generation in the national spirit is to instill in young people that the intellect, spiritual wealth, and patriotism of each of our citizens are the real strength and true wealth of our people. Sadig Garayev's novel "Heroism Number "N" sheds light on the path to strengthening the spirit of military patriotism, wider promotion of the ideology of Azerbaijanism, which is the bright path of our national statehood, and the ideas of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, and creating a broad perception of the truths reflecting our historical victory in future generations and the peoples of the world. The use of various parts of this novel in textbooks, especially their translation into foreign languages, can create conditions for a broader and deeper understanding and promotion of Azerbaijani realities. It should be noted that in general, researches have been conducted in international journals in various directions [6;7; 8; 9; 10-18].

The main part

These works are valuable works that will play an important role in preserving our historical memory and developing our national identity. These books also reflect the skill, courage, fighting spirit, and steadfastness of the fearless, brave sons of Azerbaijan. The first chapter, called "The Sprouts of War," begins with the words of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev: "The Patriotic War is a war waged to protect the honor and dignity of the entire people, of every citizen" [2, p.46].

Writer Sadig Garayev's work "Heroism No. "N"" has a rich information content, being a newly emerged scientific-philosophical, documentary-publicistic, historical novel in the direction of accelerating the processes surrounding the Karabakh War. In the 44-day war, the front and rear fronts, the international situation, the power of the unshakable unity of the people-state-army-Supreme Commander-in-Chief - the power of the "Iron Fist", the invisible heroism of "N" in the successful continuation of military operations, the power of the Azerbaijani ideology, the vile essence of the notorious Armenians, to fully and globally approach the events, and to clearly show the truth that is the common denominator of contrasts, were not enough traditional novelistic methods. Therefore, three methods were applied in the novel "Heroism No. "N": scientific-philosophical, semi-documentary-publicistic, historical-artistic. The unity of these methods with each other, the appropriate selection and application of hadiths and the general idea, in separate parts of the plot line, requires special talent, broad fantasy, creative imagination, scientific understanding and artistic thinking from the

writer. Sadig Garayev was able to cope with this complex and difficult task in the novel. The experience he gained in depicting parallel worlds and coexisting destinies in his previous works enabled him to present separate events and images that are logically connected to each other by applying different methods of depiction.

The novel "Heroism No. "N" is not only a novel written in a new style, thanks to the unity of scientific understanding and artistic thinking, but also an interesting work of art, which is the product of great effort, equal to a unique scientific research, to obtain various information from the own language of soldiers and officers, martyrs' families, and a number of sources in order to express the historical Victory fully and truthfully, to summarize them, and to bring them into a single idea and plot line.

The events in the novel, which consists of 3 chapters in terms of volume, are developed in the chapters "War Buds", "Heroism No. "N"" and "Scattering of Existence". Chapter I begins with the writings "Oath", Chapter II "The Conversation of the Worlds", and Chapter III "Victory Day". The buds of war open, the soldier takes an oath, goes to the front and shows heroism, achieves victory, the occupation is dispersed, and the sun of victory rises. The work, as a prologue, presents the essence of the "Azerbaijanism ideology" that has triumphed over 200 years of Armenian fascism. These writings are a joint, harmonious example of prose and poetry, create the unity of the chapters, illuminate their essence and should be especially appreciated.

In the first chapter of the novel "Heroism No. "N", called "War Shoots", the causes of the war, the atrocities committed by the Armenians from time to time against our people, genocides, the occupation of our lands and the heroism of our soldiers and officers during the First Karabakh War, the "April Wars", the "Tovuz Wars", the "School of Martyrdom" of the Azerbaijani people are discussed. For the first time in our literary prose, the artistic image of the Supreme Commander-in-Chief has been revived, and the thoughts, ideas and activities of the leader of our state before the war and during the war have been illuminated on the basis of reality. At the same time, the work depicts the formation and growth of the "War Shoots" against this background.

Chapter II, entitled "Heroism No. "N", deals with the preparation for the war, planning and beginning of the battle, the breaking of the "impenetrable Ohanyan line" strengthened for 30 years by the heroic soldiers and officers of the valiant Azerbaijani Armed Forces, represented by the 2nd Army Corps and the military unit No. "N", and the liberation of our villages and cities from occupation. The path of battle of dozens of martyrs and veterans, the heroism and bravery of the N and "N" numbers they showed are described mainly on the basis of documentary and real facts.

Chapter III is called "The Dispersion of Existence". Here, the dispersion of existence is described against the backdrop of the liberation of Shusha, the end of the 30-year occupation thanks to a magnificent historical victory, and the replacement of the "Drunken Crow Dances" in the Jidir Plain with the "Xaribulbul"

festival. The holiness born from the bravery of the heroic martyrs is scattered on the tricolor flag of Azerbaijan, the power of the state, and the national and spiritual pillars of the people. The heroic school of Azerbaijaniism wins a historic, decisive victory over 200 years of Armenian fascism and its supporters. The ideas of Armenianism are scattered once and for all into non-existence, into the past. In the novel "Heroism Number 'N'", the author set as his main goal to create a broad and comprehensive image of the Second Karabakh War, which ended with our historical victory, in the peoples of the world and future generations, and by applying new, novelistic methods in literature, he wrote a new type of perfect work of art at the expense of great effort. In the novel, the original unity of general ideas, plot line and events, artistic and historical, scientific and philosophical essence, journalism, and documentary serves logical consistency.

The existence of every nation is primarily connected with the national idea or national ideas. It is as a result of one or several ideas that a national ideology arises. National ideology is a system of national views that ensures national solidarity, national integrity, and serves the continuity of harmony on the spiritual level. It includes the sovereignty of the national state, territorial integrity, protection of national-spiritual, religious values and traditions, development of science and education, national economy, and education of national patriotism. The establishment and strengthening of every independent state begins with a sense of national self-preservation, and this idea, being developed, turns into an ideological system. National ideology prevents harmful ideas coming to Azerbaijan and its people from within and from abroad, and creates national-spiritual security.

One of the components of national ideology is the concept of "Azerbaijanism". The main content of Azerbaijanism is the concept of a common homeland and civil unity. In this regard, the idea of "unity of the Azerbaijani people" and "the Republic of Azerbaijan being the common and indivisible homeland of all Azerbaijanis" is reflected in our Constitution adopted on November 12, 1995. Heydar Aliyev, who made great contributions to the development of our national ideology, made unparalleled contributions to the protection of our national-spiritual values, the nationalization of personnel, and the systematization of the ideology of Azerbaijaniism. According to his philosophical views, Azerbaijaniism means preserving national-spiritual values and benefiting from their integration into the system of universal values. Along with books and articles on our national ideology, bibliographical information sources are also of great importance. One of such works is the book "Ideology of Azerbaijaniism" [3] by Sadig Garayev, which was published and dedicated to Zafar.

In the work, the author seems to be addressing every Azerbaijani. It should be noted that since I teach the subject "Bibliography of the Azerbaijani national ideology" at the master's level, we considered it appropriate to present this appeal of the author in writing in order to make it accessible to our students. The author says:

O Azerbaijani! No matter where in the world you were born or live, you must consider Azerbaijan your homeland! You must embrace national values and statehood. You must know your native language, see yourself as a martyr or veteran in the path of an independent Republic, homeland and people! You are a sedentary, a farmer, an ancient indigenous people, and you also live from sunrise to sunset. You are at the crossroads of the East, the West, the past and the present, and also the future, you are from a world with nine climates, luminous nights, scorching sun, and three colors, you are in Azerbaijan! The good in the essence of human values, heavenly religions, and the angelic patterns in the creation of humanity have drawn lines on the face of your national existence, and have remained pure since Adam to these days. Therefore, you are on a luminous, straight, and righteous path, you are goodness in itself, you are a mature, perfect supreme people!

O Azerbaijani! Every nation has a grandfather's hearth, a grandfather's hearth, where it is always the first spring. A magnificent bonfire burned in the holy Turkish hearth, sending embers all around. You are one of those embers, or there was a giant oriental oak in the hearth, with lilacs underneath, snow on top, and you are its branches, with magnificent roots that receive light from the depths, connected to a huge trunk that braves storms and darkness, you are an Azerbaijani Turk, you are an Azerbaijani. You are strong, glorious, and integral with the brotherly peoples you have lived with in your homeland for centuries. Be proud that you are Azerbaijani! Don't forget, be proud, and be worthy that you have martyr blood in your heart! You are the leader of the caravan on the sacred road, loaded with science, culture, and spirituality, which has come from ancient times, passed through today, and is heading towards the future. You are the time of Azerbaijan in time! You are a relic of humanity and heroism of the centuries!

O Azerbaijani! Like the great, supreme, nations that built states and empires, you too have had a vast homeland throughout history, whose borders have sometimes grown and sometimes shrunk, blossomed and then faded. This is a historical law: "Truth is as strong as capital, every place has become their 'homeland'!" Our Derbent, Borchal, and Tabriz are our national longing, Yerevan is our own city. Azerbaijanism is a sacred, difficult, and honorable path, its travelers come in tumbling. Martyrs, scientists, geniuses who created national values, owners of ideas and ideas - Azerbaijani men who built statehood are the ones who make the tumbling!

O Azerbaijani! There have always been martyrdom, veterans, and schools that fought for the truth in the path of their people, homeland, state, and religion, and their heroism is filled with national memory. The first school of martyrdom of the independent state, blood, soul, and Azerbaijan was opened by the soldier of the Republic, and light has shone on our souls! Our flag has been raised with their blood, and they themselves have remained in three colors. The sun of independence has risen in our souls. Since then, martyrdom and veteranhood have been as integral as the national consciousness of the school, straight from time, circular

from space, one martyr is all of us, all of them are one, they are eternal with our flag, our land, alive.

O Azerbaijani! In your essence there is friendship, whiteness, light, sun everywhere, desire for peace. Near and far nations are your friends. However, there is also a disease called Armenianism. Never forget the atrocities, devilry, genocide they committed against our people, do not remain without a stick. Live like a neighbor, do not be a friend. Wish to meet face to face on the battlefield, do not sleep in peacetime, do not lose caution. It is your human duty to go wherever there is knowledge in the world, to help those in need. And never forget, the sun rises for Azerbaijan from Azerbaijan!

O Azerbaijani! You are a modern, free, Azerbaijani Turk, that is, you are Azerbaijani. Your language is Azerbaijani Turkish, that is, the Azerbaijani language. The word Azerbaijan has been, in the true sense, the name of your homeland, language, people, itself! Don't forget, the word Azerbaijan is your existence, your identity! Your religion is Islam, you are a Muslim. Serving the homeland, the people, the state is your duty, your duty! Service itself is the homeland! For this, you must be strong, or you must be strong again! Your strength is the strength of Azerbaijan! Strength is physical health, science, spiritual and material wealth, the ideology of Azerbaijaniness, the unity of national statehood consciousness. The stones of the homeland are the inexhaustible, true national wealth of our country!

Novelty

As noted in the "Preface" written to the book, the author of the novel, Sadiq Garayev, is able to substantiate the ideas he puts forward from a scientific perspective and to give them a figurative meaning from an artistic perspective. His scientific and artistic works are original examples of science and literature created at the junction of scientific cognition and artistic thought. The author's novels "Borderless Contrasts", "Shadows without Ownership", "Times without Ownership" and "Heroism of "N" Number" as novels written in a scientific-philosophical and artistic style have created a new path in Azerbaijani literature, and have paved the way for the emergence of different and attractive literary examples in terms of reflecting national and human values with the help of the organic unity of artistic thinking and scientific cognition. Sadiq Garayev's works are important in terms of shedding light on the global problems of nature and society with the power of science, and describing all this with the possibilities of fiction, and are valuable examples reflecting the modern level of Azerbaijani scientific and literary thought. At the same time, these works show that every successful writer, being a hardworking and professional researcher of the work is an important factor in his ability to compete with time.

The instructive advice and sayings given in the section "Simple Thoughts" in the fifth chapter of the book are valuable for every Azerbaijani. We give some examples of them:

I see that we not only cannot go beyond Bilajari, but we even return back to Gobustan.

From Adam to the Resurrection, the caravans of ownerless shadows without a captain travel a path full

of shoreless contrasts, passing through every time and place.

If the weight of the word of an Intellectual is not heavier than the words of entire deputies-officials, then He is not an Intellectual. If He is an Intellectual, then society is not a society.

Good study of students is a service to the homeland together with their parents and teachers.

The branching, umbrella shape, and trunk of trees of the same species planted in a nearby area are often similar, like twins.

Books are the most valuable wealth of mankind.

Those who seriously try to show themselves as scholars cannot learn that they know nothing until the end of their lives!

Nations that do not go into the future with the light of science either fall into the well or lose their way. Our light is fading.

The seed grows in the soil, the word grows in the memory.

Trees not only grow upwards, but also sideways...

The owners of capital are the ones who unite the world, the causes of war.

Bird nests themselves are strange worlds. They create in man a sense of respect for labor and love for nature.

Give me a stone, and I will run out of stones,

As if the devil,

He gathered them for us to throw.

Dogs can make themselves be perceived as the most loyal friends, even though they are lost [2, p.353].

In the sixth chapter, our attention was attracted by the ideas given in the "Life Tablets" section. These ideas can play an important role in the patriotic and educated growth of the younger generation.

Each village has its own unique atmosphere. This aura is formed not only by geographical conditions, natural factors, but also by the thoughts and actions of the people living there. For example, the village of Khanliglar smells of paradise.

The road to our village, Khanliglar, is beautiful in every season of the year.

Everyone's village is a paradise for them, a source of holiness.

I have seen Mount Ağrı from many angles - from the Salvarti Mountains, from Iğdir, from Doğu Bayazid.

However, it does not look as charming from anywhere as it does from Sharur.

We grew up looking at this mountain, we knew it as our own.

We know summer and winter by the decrease and increase of its snow, and we also predict the weather with it.

Writer Sadig Garayev wanted to convey to his readers once again with the voice of his heart the love for his homeland and his native land:

Our mountain.

The most native, beautiful landscape in the world is our yard in the grandfather's hearth.

Land, plants, neighbors, trees, crops, chickens, turkeys,

Vineyard,

Rose, corn, watermelon arch...
 Mulberry tree, grass blade,
 Swallow's nest on our balcony,
 Coma of childhood memories,
 Holy castle of the eternal soul...
 Wooden rifle, string pistol,
 Fugitive shooting,
 World war...
 All native, different...

The rocks of Nakhchivan are violet, henna-colored,
 Sometimes their chests are ice-cold,
 Sometimes their partridges are nests.

In our books, especially in the novels "Borderless Contrasts" and "Shadows Without Ownership", the forced expulsion of Azerbaijanis from the Vedi, Dere-layiz districts of Western Azerbaijan, Chobankara, and Garalar villages, the tortures inflicted on them, their resettlement in Nakhchivan, Iran, and Turkey, and the hardships they endured are presented with real events and artistic descriptions [2, p. 379].

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that one of the components of the national ideology is the concept of "Azerbaijanism". The main content of Azerbaijanism is the concept of a common homeland, civic unity. In this regard, the idea of "unity of the Azerbaijani people" and "the Republic of Azerbaijan being the common and indivisible homeland of all Azerbaijanis" was reflected in our Constitution adopted on November 12, 1995. Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, who made great contributions to the development of our national ideology, made unparalleled contributions to the protection of our national and spiritual values, the nationalization of personnel, and the systematization of the ideology of Azerbaijanism. According to his philosophical views, Azerbaijanism means preserving national-spiritual values and benefiting from their integration into the system of universal values.

As a result of the successful domestic and foreign policy pursued by our invincible commander, our esteemed President, Supreme Commander-in-Chief Ilham Aliyev for many years, we further strengthened our positions and in 2019, we uttered the words "Karabakh is Azerbaijan and a Call" from a high international podium, and in 2020, we gave a worthy response to the enemy with the Iron Fist based on the unity of the people and power, ensuring the territorial integrity of our independent state. Azerbaijan's "Victory Day" was written in bright and large letters before our eyes.

Our successes in the field of diplomacy also played an exceptional role in achieving victory over the enemy. The fact that the President of Azerbaijan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief Mr. Ilham Aliyev responded with restraint and solid facts to the pressures of circles supporting the Armenians and to the biased questions of the press representatives of leading foreign countries at a time when the fighting was going on, brought Azerbaijan success in the war started by Armenia[4].

The works of the scientist and writer Sadig Garayev are very valuable in our victory and are valuable sources of information in educating the younger generation in the national spirit.

References

1. Heydar Aliyev: Bibliographic reference book (2003) / Compiled by A. Khalafov, S. Sadigova.-Baku: Baku University Press, 455 p. (in english) https://anl.az/el_en/book2013/I-34796.pdf.
2. Qarayev, S. (2024) Azərbaycançılıq məfkurəsi.-Bakı: "Tiçprint", 418 s.
3. Qarayev, S. (2023) "N" sayılı qəhrəmanlıq:(Tarixi roman). - Bakı: "Tiçprint", 376 s.
4. Sadigova S.A. (2021)The iron fist is a symbol of the unity of the people and the government and our solidarity... // www.moderator.az. - 21 mart <https://moderator.az/az/read/370042/>
5. Sadiqova S.A. (2016) Socio-political information resources:Textbook. - Baku: Mutarcim, 126 p.
6. Sadigova S.A.(2016) Information resource dedicated to Yerevan-Azerbaijani literature //Materials of the scientific-practical conference of young researchers on the topic "Material and spiritual heritage of Yerevan" Baku, May 25, 2016, Baku: "Bizim Nesil" GRIA PU, P.107-112. <http://web2.anl.az:81/read/page.php?bibid=vtls000500385>
7. Sadigova S.A. (2019) The place of primary sources on the Iravan Khanate in the information provision of field specialists // Scientific work: Monthly international scientific journal on the humanities DOI:10.36719/ AEM/2007-2019\48\55-58.ISSN2663-4619.-№9(48), S.55-58. https://aem.az/uploads/files/2019-11/1574834363_elmi-ish_9_48.pdf Journal indexing: Cite Factor Academic Scientific Journals, DOI, Coogole Scholar, Academia.edu, Azerbaijan Press Council, İnternational Standart Serial Number İnternational Centre.
8. Sadigova S.A (2021) General aspects of bibliography in the conditions of the information society (in English)// American Scientific Journal Vol 1 № (46) / Journal New York, Elmhurst AV, Queens, NY, United States PИHЦ (2016), eLIBRARY, World Cat, Индексация DOI .-2021, №1(46) P.4-8 <https://american-issue.infohttps://archive.american-issue.info/index.php/asj/issue/view/7/7>
9. Sadigova, S.A. (2021 b) Information supply of state bodies: modern condition and perspectives (in English)// The 6th International scientific and practical conference "World science: problems, prospects and innovations" (February 23-25, 2021) Perfect Publishing, Toronto, Canada. 792 p. Toronto, Canada.- P.89-98 ISBN 978-1-4879-3793-5 <https://sci-conf.com.ua/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/WORLD-SCIENCE-PROBLEMS-PROSPECTS-AND-INNOVATIONS-23-25.02.2021.pdf> <https://sci-conf.com.ua/>
10. Sadigova S.A.(2021) Study of the flow of documents and information about the Karabakh Khanate //Karabakh International Congress of Modern Research in Social and Human Sciences, 17-19 June, P.300-301.

https://mifologiya.az/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/KARABAGH_Abstract_Book.pdf

<https://www.karabaghconference.com/>

11. Sadigova S.A (2021) Modern forms and methods of bibliographic activity in libraries (in english) // ISSN 2524-0935 НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ «АРХИВАРИУС» Киев. Том 7№ 2 (56) P.12-16 <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/modern-forms-and-methods-of-bibliographic-activity-in-libraries/view-erhttps://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44761241> <https://archivarius.org.ua/eLIBRARY>, [Ссылка на журнал в Elibrary](#), [Index Copernicus](#), [Google Scholar](#), [Ссылка на журнал в Scholar](#), [Ссылка на журнал в ICI](#), [Ulrich's Web](#), [DOAJ](#), [КиберЛенинка](#), [World Cat](#), [Cite Factor 1.04\(2021\)](#) [Crossref](#), [Индексация DOI](#) [Импакт-фактор 6.109](#) [Просмотреть импакт-фактор](#) [https://archivarius.org.ua/Ar-](https://archivarius.org.ua/Archive/new/Arkhivarius_20_02_2021.pdf)

12. Sadigova, S.A. (2018) National bibliography of Azerbaijan in the global information space: Monograph (dedicated to the 100th anniversary of the establishment of Baku State University). - Baku, ADPU publishing house, 305 p.

13. Sadigova S.A. (2010) Thematic bibliographical information sources dedicated to historical science//Scientific News of the Azerbaijan University of Languages, Baku, No. 2, pp. 413-420.

14. Sadigova S.A. (2018) Initial resources on socio-political information(In english) // European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences.-Vyana (Avstriya) №6, S.60-62 http://ppublishing.org/upload/iblock/404/EJH-6_2018-cor4.pdf The journal has the GIF impact factor .211 for 2017.

15. Sadigova, S.A. (2021) General aspects of bibliography in the conditions of the information society (In english) // American Scientific Journal Vol 1 № (46) / Journal New York, Elmhurst AV, Queens, NY, United States РИНЦ (2016), eLIBRARY, World Cat, Индексация DOI .-2021, №1(46) P.4-8 <https://american-issue.info> <https://archive.american-issue.info/index.php/asj/issue/view/7/7>

16. Sadigova S.A.(2019) The place of primary sources on the Iravan Khanate in the information provision of field specialists // Scientific work: Monthly international scientific journal on the humanities DOI: 10.36719/AEM/2007-2019\48\55-58. ISSN2663-4619.№9(48), s.55-58 https://aem.az/uploads/files/2019-11/1574834363_elmi-ish_9_48.pdf Journal indexing: Cite Factor Academic Scientific Journals, DOI, Coogle Scholar, Academia.edu, Azerbaijan Press Council, International Standart Serial Number International Centre.

17. Sadigova S.A., Ismayilov N.I. (2022) Synergetic foundations of the methodology of modern bibliography // Scientific and theoretical almanac Grani: History. - Ukraine, Volume 25. - №6. GRANI25(6). - P.45-51 <https://grani.org.ua/index.php/journal/issue/view/191/ab>

18. Sadigova S., Mammadova Z. (2023) Effectiveness of using archival documents in the primary sources of information about the İrevan Khanate (in english) // Akademik tarih ve düşünce dergisi..Türkiyə <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/atdd> /issue/81046/1446989 Cilt:10, Sayı 6, 2819-2826